

DISCONTINUOUS REINFORCED ALUMINIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS : AN OVERVIEW

Céline Carré - Yann Barboux

AEROSPATIALE - Centre Commun de Recherches Louis Blériot
BP 76 - 92152 SURESNES CEDEX

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the different technologies of fabrication of Particulates Reinforced Aluminium Matrix Composites - Powder Metallurgy, Spray Deposition & Casting - and the main results obtained at AEROSPATIALE in the evaluation of demonstration parts.

More particularly the mechanical properties, including fatigue and damage tolerance, of a non rotating star of the AS 350 helicopter forged in P/M X2080 reinforced with 15 wt% SiC particules and of a flared housing of the TIGER helicopter cast in Duralcan A 357 reinforced with 20 wt% SiC particules are discussed and compared to results obtained on extrusions in Cospray 7075 reinforced with 15 wt% SiC particules.

The potential applications on aerospace structures are presented and the cost efficiency of the replacement of conventional metals is discussed.

Keywords : Aluminium Matrix Composites - SiC Particules - Powder Metallurgy - Investment Casting - Spray Deposition - Aerospace

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the particular compromise of physical and mechanical properties they offer, which may be tailored for specific applications varying the matrix, the nature, the shape and the volume fraction of reinforcement, Aluminium Matrix Composites (AMCs) present a strong interest for space and aeronautic structures [1].

AEROSPATIALE has been investigating particles reinforced metals for about 10 years now, starting with the DWA and ARCO - now APMC - materials, and the overall budget for the study of AMCs' was multiplied by ten during that decade.

During these ten years, and as the knowledge of the behaviour of these composites was improving, the field of potential applications on our structures was getting more and more precise, confirming the interest of the Metal Matrix Composites for many parts currently fabricated in Aluminium or Titanium alloys or even in Organic Matrix Composites.

In the competition with conventional metals, AMCs', because they can be shaped by conventional manufacturing processes - forging, extrusion, rolling, machining or casting - seem particularly attractive for the fabrication of bulky parts designed in stiffness.

In the competition with organic matrix composites AMC's, if they cannot lead to the same weight reductions, present many advantages : they offer isotropic properties which allow them to be used in complex shape parts with stresses in three directions, they do not suffer from moisture absorption nor from low energy impacts, they have good thermal and electrical conductivities and, most of all, their cost is much lower, or expected to be.

And that is the main point : what is, or what will be the price of the AMC's in a production phase ? On this, will significantly depend the field of potential applications. With a price of billet of US\$ 30 per pound, which was usually announced some years ago for the Powder Metallurgy (P/M) products, only the replacement of Titanium alloys on some parts may be considered. If the price comes down to US\$ 5 to 10 per pound then the replacement of aluminium alloys becomes cost effective in many cases.

That is why AEROSPATIALE, in the mid eighties, decided to evaluate alternative processes of fabrication of AMC's and more particularly the Spray Deposition, based on the Osprey technology, and the Duralcan casting process.

In the following chapters the results of the evaluation of the three technologies - P/M, Spray Deposition and Investment Casting of Duralcan products - are presented and discussed.

2. POWDER METALLURGY

2.1. Chronology

The study of P/M AMC's started at AEROSPATIALE in 1983, with the evaluation of extruded products first from DWA and then from ARCO in the USA. In the early stage of their development these materials, while they exhibited high stiffness, high strength and good thermal properties, were very brittle, with fracture toughness values much lower than the matrix, not suitable for aircraft structural applications.

From 1986 to 1989 a joint development work with PECHINEY, supported by the french Ministry of Research, resulted in the optimisation of the manufacturing process at a reduced scale of a helicopter component in Al. 6061 reinforced with 15 and 25 % of SiC particles, having significantly improved levels of ductility and fracture toughness (Table 1).

Vf SiCp (%)	TYS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	E (GPa)	K1c (MPa√m)
15	350	420	8	95	22
25	375	470	3,5	110	17

Table 1 - Mechanical Properties on an Upper Casing of Main Transmission Gear Box in AMC

In 1989, while continuing the cooperation with the french aluminium producer on the Spray Deposition technology, AEROSPATIALE decided to confirm the good results obtained with P/M products by tests on a real component. A cooperation work started with FORGES DE BOLOGNE, ALCOA FORGING DIVISION, with the objective of making a demonstration non rotating star of AS 350 helicopter in ALCOA X2080 + 15% SiCp material (figure 1).

The main criteria for the selection of this part were the availability of the die at FORGES DE BOLOGNE and the complex shape of the component representative of all the technological difficulties encountered in forging and machining operations.

The detailed results of this cooperation work, which started by the optimisation of the parameters for die forging on a simple shape stringer, have already been reported [2], only the main conclusions are presented hereafter.

2.2. AS 350 Non Rotating Star forged in X2080 + 15% SiCp

The part was forged from a 5" diameter extruded bar in three major steps : the open die preform, the blocker die forging and the finish die forging operation.

Figure 1 - Non Rotating Star of AS 350 in X2080 + 15% SiCp after machining

The X2080 matrix is a 2000 serie P/M alloy whose typical chemistry is Al - 3.8%Cu - 1.8%Mg - 0.2%Zr. The volume fraction of SiC particles reinforcement is 15%. The part was heat-treated to the T4 temper : solution heat treatment at 490°C for 4 hours, cold water quench and 4 days natural ageing.

The distribution of SiC particles in the matrix was found to be homogeneous, but, surprisingly, the particle size distribution exhibited a large scatter band, from 3 to 22µm with a mean value of 12µm.

The evaluation of mechanical properties demonstrated a good compromise of properties, and more particularly confirmed the high fracture toughness values announced by ALCOA, close to those of 7075 T 73 alloy, and evidenced a very good behaviour in fatigue initiation and fatigue crack growth (table 2).

Material	TYS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	E (GPa)	K1c (MPa√m)	Fatigue (1) (MPa)	Crack growth (2) (mm / cy)
X2080+SiC	330	490	8	96	24,5	200	3.10 ⁻⁴
7075 T73	424	497	12,4	71	32	180	5.10 ⁻⁴

(1) Maximum Stress on notched specimen (Kt=2,3) in constant amplitude (R=0,1) at 10⁵ cycles

(2) Crack growth rate in constant amplitude (R=0,1) for ΔK = 15 MPa√m

Table 2 - Mechanical properties of the AS 350 non rotating star in CMAI and 7075 T 73

On the basis of these results it was decided to have a cost analysis of this part in AMC in comparison with the same part in Titanium Ti 6-4 alloy and to carry out a full scale component test on a fatigue bench.

The results of the cost analysis are reported in table 3.

	Ti 6-4	X2080 + SiC
Weight of the part (kg)	8,5	5,2
Raw Material	640	625
Process	700	440
Machining	365	210
Total cost (US \$)	1705	1275

Table 3 - Cost analysis for the non rotating star : comparison between AMC and Ti 6-4

Using the development cost of AMCs' for calculation (i.e. US \$ 60 per pound) the cost analysis indicates a 25 % cost saving of the X2080 + SiCp part versus the Titanium part. This cost saving may reach 53 % if we consider a production cost of US \$ 15 per pound as it is announced by ALCOA.

On the other hand, the results of the full scale fatigue test demonstrate a 20 % improvement of the fatigue life as compared to the present series part in 7075 T73.

Thus it can be concluded that P/M AMCs' may today be considered for parts designed in stiffness and fatigue. In this case AMCs' are a good alternative to Titanium alloys for the replacement of high strength Aluminium alloys : they can provide a 10 to 40 % weight saving, depending on the design of the part, while being 20 to 50 % less expensive than Titanium alloys.

3. INVESTMENT CASTING OF DURALCAN COMPOSITES

3.1. Chronology

P/M AMCs' are attractive for structural parts. However there are applications for which only an increase of stiffness may be interesting and for which high levels of ductility or fracture toughness are not a concern. For these non structural applications a cheapest process of production of reinforced parts is of a prime interest.

That is why AEROSPATIALE decided in 1987 to start the evaluation of DURALCAN products [3].

Table 4 presents the results obtained on extruded bars from DURALCAN billets. As a matter of fact, at that time the development of the investment casting of DURALCAN AMCs' was not achieved and it was only envisaged to use the AMCs' billets as raw material for extrusion and forging as for the P/M process.

Material	TYS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	E (GPa)	K1c (MPa \sqrt{m})
2014 + 15% SiCp	420	440	1,4	90	-
2014 + 15% Al ₂ O ₃	460	490	1,4	95	14
6061 + 20% Al ₂ O ₃	345	375	1,8	93	19

Table 4 - Mechanical Properties on extruded bars of Duralcan material

If the elongation and fracture toughness values were actually too low for structural applications, the Young's modulus and the overall compromise of properties, including fatigue and thermal cycling, were very attractive for non structural parts designed in stiffness.

So when CERCAST, in 1989, presented us the process of investment casting of DURALCAN billets we decided to start an evaluation on a real component.

3.2. TIGER helicopter flared housing in Duralcan A 357 + 20% SiCp

This part was selected because of its size, because it was representative of major casting difficulties and because the tools were available at CERCAST , allowing a comparison with the same part in conventional A 357 alloy.

Figure 2 - Flared housing of TIGER helicopter in Duralcan A 357 + 20% SiCp by CERCAST

The Non Destructive Evaluation (X Ray) of the part does not evidence any redhibitory defect. However the microstructural investigation shows SiC free areas in the thicker zones of the part. These areas may be detected by Electrical Conductivity measurements : the electrical conductivity is around 20 MS/m in the SiC free zones and around 13 MS/m in the reinforced zones. Some large porosities are present in the frontier area between reinforced and non reinforced zones which were not detected by X Radiography.

Table 5 presents the results of the characterization of the AMC part in comparison with the non reinforced A 357 part [4].

Material	TYS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	E (GPa)
Duralcan A 357 + 20% SiCp	-	310	0,1	94
A 357	280	340	6	71

Table 5 - Mechanical properties of the TIGER flared housing casting in CMAI and A 357 alloy

The objective in term of improvement of stiffness is reached. However the very low ductility, even lower than for extruded bars in DURALCAN, will limit the use of such products on aeronautic components to some satellite applications or electronic packagings; improvements should be searched through optimisation of the thermal treatment, modification of the microstructure of the matrix or modification of the size, shape or nature of the ceramic particles.

4. SPRAY DEPOSITION

In 1989, after the promising results obtained on P/M AMCs', and while continuing the development work in cooperation with FORGES DE BOLOGNE, AEROSPATIALE decided to start the evaluation of a new process, the spray deposition based on the OSPREY technology, which was then announced as a serious competitor for the Powder Metallurgy technique, leading to the same quality but for a much lower price.

In parallel with a first evaluation of the existing COSPRAY products from ALCAN in cooperation with the MBB Central Laboratories in Munich [5], AEROSPATIALE, MBB (now Deutsche Aerospace), ALCAN, PECHINEY together with BAe, OTTO FUCHS, INSA de Lyon and LNETI started a CEC sponsored BRITE-EURAM programme untitled " Low Cost MMCs' Made by Spray Deposition" [6] with the objective of optimising the parameters of the process to produce AMCs' with properties taylored for aerospace applications.

The macrostructure of COSPRAY product is illustrated on figure 3 for an extruded bar in 7075 + 15% SiCp. The results of the mechanical tests in the T6 temper are shown in table 6 in comparison with the results on P/M products.

Figure 3 - Macrostructure of a 7075 + 15% SiCp COSPRAY extruded bar

Material	TYS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	E (GPa)	K1c (MPa√m)
Cospray 7075 + 15% SiCp	515	570	2,5	96	13
P/M 6061 + 15% SiCp	350	420	8	95	22
P/M X2080 + 15% SiCp	415	545	6,5	100	20

Table 6 - Mechanical properties of extruded bars of the different processes

The OSPREY spray deposition route offers the same advantages than DURALCAN or Powder Metallurgy routes : The Young modulus is increased by about 30% through an addition of 15 vol % SiC maintaining the high Ultimate Tensile Strength. Nevertheless, ductility and fracture toughness are lowered in comparison with the P/M process, but this may be related to the high strength of the matrix. The properties have yet to be optimised through an optimisation of the matrix composition, the repartition of ceramic particles or the heat treatment conditions. Besides the development work carried out in the Brite Euram programme has demonstrated that the spray deposition process could allow volume fractions of reinforcement as high as 20%.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Because of their specific properties Particles Reinforced Aluminium Matrix Composites are particularly adapted for applications designed in stiffness, competing with Aluminium and Titanium alloys. As examples we can indicate :

- on aircrafts : upper wing stringers, floor beams, structural struts,
- on helicopters : housings, but also some mechanical parts,
- on space structures : fittings (with the benefit of a low Coefficient of Thermal Expansion - CTE) and stringers in compression loaded areas

Among the different technologies of production of such AMCs' Powder Metallurgy is the only one today having reached a degree of development which allows the use on structural parts. The results obtained on real forged components demonstrate that P/M AMCs' may be used on structural parts designed in stiffness, with high levels of loading - even in fatigue - in replacement of Aluminium alloys and in competition with Titanium alloys. In that case the use of an AMC may result in a 10 to 40% weight reduction and a 20 to 50 % cost reduction.

Investment casting of DURALCAN products results in parts of a relatively good quality with an improved modulus of elasticity. This process, cheapest than P/M process, is of interest for non structural applications for which a high stiffness and a low CTE are of concern. However the poor ductility and the low fracture toughness of these materials are a strong limitation for structural applications.

The spray deposition process leads to promising results. However it is still in a rather early stage of development, and improvements are needed as far as ductility and fracture toughness are concerned.

They seem possible through the optimisation of the matrix composition and of the repartition of ceramic particles. Besides recent developments in the frame of a Brite Euram programme have demonstrated that this process could allow volume fractions of reinforcement as high as 20%.

At this stage of the development work the cost interest of this technology as compared to P/M products, which was a main argument in its favour, is still a matter of discussion.

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